

The Tiruvallam Temple a Historical Perspective

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ABSTRACT

A rich history may be found in both the Hindu temple and the faith it represents. Its origin has been a source of contention, with some attributing it to the burial site and others attributing it to the hero stones,¹ others to the hero stones of old,² and so on. There is no doubt that in pre-historic times the worship of images in the open, possibly under trees, preceded the erection of temples.

Keywords : *The Hindu temple, the Tiruvallam Temple , Devdram, Teivam cernta pararaivempu, alamar kadavul, ect.,*

INTRODUCTION

The Tiruvallam is in Villupuram district about 6 km., north-west of Villupuram. It is a small village and the temple of Bilvanatheswara is in the heart of the village.⁴⁹ Tiruvallam has 1,957 people as its population. Some accounts say that it was here Appar renounced the Jain faith, although the Periyapuram locates the event at Tiruvadi. The temple is dedicated to Abhiramesvara and the three Tamil saints have sung about it in the *Devdram*. Two of them describe it as situated on the western bank of the river (Pamba) instead of the eastern bank. The river is in consequence said to have changed its course to the other side of the temple so that the words of the saints might not be falsified. The Pamba is known to have changed her course several times. The temple contains a large number of Chola inscriptions.

A river by name Pamba flows along the north of the temple. The Pamba River irrigates the lands in the village, presenting a very greening scene. The mango, jack and plantain groves mixed with paddy and sugarcane cultivation add a cheerful look and attraction to the visitors. Thus, Tiruvallam is a very fertile village.⁵⁰

The Area

This village is bounded on the east by Panaiyapuram, west and south by Valudavur and north by Villupuram taluk. It lies between 15°5' and 12°30' of the north latitude and 78°37' and 80° of the east longitude.⁵¹

The village Tiruvallam has an area of 2.32 square miles. It is well-connected with roads and railways. The Villupuram station is an important railway junction in the Villupuram-Tiruchirappalli railway line. The state highway is running through tin's town and is connected to the important cities in the Cuddalore region from the northern districts of Tamil Nadu.

Since the river Pamba River runs across the village, the soil, of the taluk is more fertile and 70 per cent is alluvial, 23 per cent regar and 7 percent aremacias. The climatic condition of the village is normal. It has maximum 39.40°C and 32.08°C minimum temperature throughout the year. The average rain fall is 50 to 53 inches. Due, to its location near the sea, the taluk is getting more rain every year.⁵²

Hindus, Muslims and Christians live in this village, but the majority of them are Hindus. The majority of the people speak Tamil as their mother tongue. Telugu and Urdu are also the spoken languages of the people, who belong to the respective communities and in the village.

The economy of the village is fully based on agriculture. Since the village is located on the banks of Pamba River, paddy is cultivated regularly in 99 percent of the land. It is the main source of income in the village. Besides, ragi, sugarcane and groundnut are also raised as seasonal crops in this region. The river Pamba is well-connected with many irrigational channels feeding water to the agricultural fields in the village. Besides there are a number of rural industries which help to uplift the Economy of the people. Silk and cotton handloom societies in this village give considerable jobs to the people of the village. Sugar mill and brick industries are also run by the cooperative institutions in this village.⁵³

From the literature and inscriptions, it is known that this village came under the control of the Pallavas, Cholas, Pandyas and Vijayanagar rulers. In the post-independent India, Tiruvallam region was first located in the district of South Arcot. When South Arcot district was bifurcated for administrative convenience as Cuddalore and Villupuram districts, at present it is a village panchayat in Villuburam taluk. Having analysed the evidences, it is clear that the name of the village Tiruvallam is called in the same name from the very beginning to this date.

Origin of Temples

The Tamils were a God-fearing people. They believed in the existence of a supreme power which they called *Irai* (Supreme King), who protected and preserved them from dangers and evils. He was conceived after the living King (the protector of his people) whom they called *Ko* (King) and housed him in *Koil* (palace). The omni-present God, the protector of all, therefore,

was also housed in *Koil* (abode of God) which was conceived after the residence of the living King. As a place of worship, the temple (*Koil*) attracts thousands of people. It acts as a hub where people's religious inclinations and sentiments can find a healthy release. The devotees' hearts become divine and pure as a result of their temple worship.⁴ For, it provides a link between man and God and the earthly life and divine life. Thus, man in his quest for God, the invisible, built temples as visual symbols of divine presence. It is intended to give a concrete shape to an abstract concept. The *garba graham* of a temple not only enshrines the idol of gods and goddesses but also symbolizes the divine essence.

A genuine fervor for devotion was sparked by the concept of God and the intent behind reverence. This called for a worshipable object. The primitive Tamils favored plants, trees, and groves as ideal objects of worship since they were so useful. The beauty of trees' exterior forms not only mesmerized the populace but also gave refuge under their swaying boughs..⁵ Further, there was a general conception among the early people that the godly element was actively at work in places of natural beauty. (Hence, the tree was sacred to the Tamils, because it was the abode of spirits and gods. They even believed that gods used to reside in the hallows of trees.⁶

*Teivam cernta pararavempu*⁷, *alamar kadavul*,⁸ *alamar celvar*⁹ and *kadampamar celvan*¹⁰ clearly indicate the association of Gods with trees. Besides, many other trees like *arasu* (pipal), *iratti* (zizyphus), *pala* (jack), *vgai* (albizzia), *vanni* (prosopis), and *vengai* (pterocarpus) were also worshipped as the abodes of spirits and Gods¹¹ The prominent Gods of the Tamils, namely, Siva and Vishnu are associated with the banyan tree.¹² These help us to suggest that the practice of worshipping trees as abodes or resting places of Gods was in vogue among the early Tamils To safeguard the place of worship, they had roofed galleries or raised enclosure walls around the place of worship.¹³ Offerings made to a banyan tree surrounded by a brick enclosure illustrate this.¹⁴ *AlakKoil* and *nalakKoil* were temples probably known after the trees.¹⁵ The sacred tree (*sthalavriksha*) of the Nataraja Temple, Chidambaram, still today is tillai (acquillaria), that of the Ekambaranatha Temple, Kanchi is amra and that of the Sundaesvara temple, Madurai, is the *Kadamba*, which are the reminiscences of the association of trees with old temples. Hence, in the beginning, worship was in the open air, and Gods had no temples¹⁶

But over time, instead of identifying a particular tree as a place of worship, a conical stone or a wooden pillar known as *kandu*¹⁷ or a jaw bone of a shark was planted under the tree or in a common open place to identify the place of worship. This form of worship was adopted perhaps to get the concentration of the mind. Like a tree, *kandu* itself represented the deity. (Some believe that the platform, the *Kandu*, and the tree were collectively known as *podiyil* or *Ambalam*.¹⁸ The term *Ambalam* indicates a structure. The inheritors of Dravijian culture on the West coast even today call the temple *Ambalam*. *Ambalam* was probably the corruption of anbu Warn (home of love) which was a common place of worship known as *podu-il*. Its modified form was *podiyil*. In the Sangam literature, there are many references to *podiyil* in which Kandu is placed for worship.¹⁹ As a sacred place, *podiyil* was cleaned and smoothed with wet cow-

dung paste by young women who, after a dip in the bathing, lit a perpetual lamp.²⁰ It becomes evident that the *Ambalam* or the *podiyil* was the earliest form of a temple in the Tamil country.

Another origin of the temple can be seen in the cult of the dead. The ancient Tamils worshipped their dead ancestors. They believed in the existence and efficacy of the spirit of the dead. These spirits were supposed to cause epidemics and famines. If the Gods were not appeased, there would be no rain and the consequence was a failure of crops. Therefore, to pacify the dead, a simple ring of stone was formed around the grave.²¹ It was to prevent the ghosts from rising above the grave. They thought that their dead became stone or *nadukal*.²² The burial site, a kind of mark, was identified for a long period and the ancestors were remembered. This form of worship is called *nadukal* worship which was one of the phases of ancestor worship.

The surviving written works and monuments demonstrate how ancestral worship evolved into ritualistic religious worship with megalithic structures. The megalithic remains that have recently been discovered in several locations around Tamil Nadu show us how carefully *nadukal* was constructed. The steps leading to *nadukal* worship included choosing a stone, scheduling an opportune time for carving the image at the chosen location, and lastly sanctifying it as a deity for worship.²³ Therefore, as a mark of respect, a canopy of cloth was placed over it, decorated with peacock feathers²⁴ and it was offered flower garlands.²⁵ Then, a lamp burning in ghee was placed early in the morning.²⁶ To please the hero of the *nadukal*, toddy, the favorite liquor was offered, the lamb was sacrificed and *tudi*, a musical instrument, was played.²⁷ The name of the hero, his exploits, and the causes of his death were also inscribed on the slab. Such memorials with inscriptions were known as *eluthudaiyanadukal*.²⁸ Generally, it was surrounded by an enclosure with a spear and shield planted in front of it.²⁹ It was perhaps to give protection to the hero-stone and to show the valor of the hero. Such acts reveal their reverence for the dead. Those heroes were worshipped probably as their war Gods. Ancestor worship certainly continued as another undercurrent beneath the formal religion of the Tamils.³⁰

History of Temples

In the last phase of the Sangam age, the temples were variously called *katavukatinagar*³¹ and *murugankottam*.³² The temple of Muruga was also referred to as *katampamar celvan katinagar*.³³ Those early temples, are said to be made of perishable materials like brick, bamboo, or wood.³⁴ The statement *suduman ongiya nedunagar*³⁵ indicates the use of burnt bricks. In addition, mortar was also used in erecting structures as it helped durability. This is substantiated by material evidence in Tamil Nadu belonging to a period immediately before or after Christ,³⁶ Perhaps by the end of the Sangam age, Senganan, a Chola King, is said to have constructed seventy temples (*madak Koils*) for Siva.³⁷ The shape of these temples could not be traced, for their material remains are not available.

Different materials were employed for the definite purpose of conveying specific meaning. For instance, brick was the substance of the spiritual altar signifying the sacrifice, wood was the substance of the world, and tree and stone, were the substance of the mountain.³⁸ As beauty was the most sacred thing on the earth, it found its eloquent expression more in the construction of temples than in the houses of men. Therefore, the structural form of temples was shaped and reshaped from time to time till they attained grandeur.

The existing early temples are simple in structure. They are like the *vchaityas*. It is held that these structures had the influences of the earlier Buddhist structures.³⁹ In fact, Buddhism had established its hold over the Tamil country before the Pallava Age, even during the Sangam age.⁴⁰

At the outset of the Kalabhra age, the old political and social structure disappeared. The old pattern of religious life was eclipsed by the new religious activities. However, it did not last long. With the ascendancy of the Pallavas under Simhavishnu in the north and the revival of Pandyas under Kadunkon in the south, the Kalabhra hold over the Tamil country was reduced to insignificance by the close of the sixth century A.D. The early *bhakti* movement in the Tamil country helped the Hindu spiritual life, expansion of religious activities, and extension of temple construction.⁴¹ It resulted in the emergence of Tamil cities.

The arrival of the Pallavas and the Pandyas on the political scene heralded a new epoch in the history of temple architecture. They intensified temple building activities and introduced the "durable" stone as building materials from the sixth century A.D.⁴² This is evident from the Mandagapattu inscription of Mahendravarman which states that without timber, brick, mortar, and metal, the temple for the Trimurtis - Brahma, Vishnu and Siva was caused to be constructed by Vichitrachitta.⁴³ He is said to have scooped out a large number of rock-cut temples throughout his kingdom. Similarly, the Pandyas also excavated large, medium as well as small rock-cut temples.⁴⁴ In these temples, there was less scope for the conduct of rituals and festivals on a grand scale and the employment of a large number of servants. In the absence of these, there was little scope for the introduction of administration.

The next phase of temple architecture is the monolithic cut-out temples. Hewn out of single rocks, they were known as *rathas*. The Pallava model of such monuments is seen in Mahabalipuram. Though the; Pandyas were not the masters of such a style, their contribution to the monolithic style cannot be neglected. They have an illustrious example at Vettuvan Koil, Kalugumalai.⁴⁵ As these are small individual structures occupying little space, there is again less scope for the conduct of rituals and festivals on a grand scale. Therefore, the employment of a large number of servants to administer their affairs does not arise.

This was followed by the erection of structural temples this novel method started with the accession of Rajasimha Pallava. He is said to have built the Shore Temple at Mahabalipuram and the Kailasanatha and Vaikunthaperumal Temples at Kanchi. In between the Pallava and Pandya

Kingdoms, the Muttarayars appear to have built some of their famous structures. Thus, temples covering a large area "with additional beautification as centers of worship came into being. In reality, conceived as centers of worship, rituals, and festivals on a grand scale might have been conducted in these temples. Following the Pallavas, the Cholas, the early Pandyas, and the Muttarayars, built many such structures throughout their empire. Vijayalaya Chola built the now-famous Nishumbasudani (Durga) Temple in Tanjore. Rajaraja I and Rajendra I followed this model. The Rajarajesvaram built by Rajaraja I at Tanjore, the Gangaikondacholisvarar built by Rajendra I at Gangaikondacholapuram; and Airavadesvarar by Rajaraja II "at Darasuram illustrious example of structural temples. The Pandyas also built several structural temples of moderate size. Their grand edifices built perhaps from the ninth century could be seen in their dominion. Some of them are Vatapatrasayi Temple, Srivilliputtur; Varagunisvara Temple, Radhapuram; Siva Temple at Amsamudram; Tiruttalisvara Temple, Tiruppattur; Vijayanarayanan Temple, Nanguneri and Lakshminarayana Temple, Sinnamanur.⁴⁶ The practice of constructing magnificent temple complexes on a grand scale giving importance to the outer *gopuras*, *prakaras*, and *mandapas* coincided with the ascendancy of the second Pandyan empire.⁴⁷ Constructing magnificent temple complexes on a grand scale giving importance to the outer *gopuras*, *prakaras*, and *mandapas* coincided with the ascendancy of the second Pandyan empire.⁴⁷

The tradition of constructing and embellishing temples was continued by the later Pandyas, the Vijayanagar emperors, and the Nayak rulers. After the 18th century, the construction of huge temples received a set-back in the South with the appearance of the struggle between the Western powers for supremacy and the final establishment of British sovereignty. But the remarkable feature of the history of Hindu temples is that, in South India, they have not suffered much from the ravages of invaders and iconoclasts, with the result that as compared with the rest of India, the South has fortunately preserved its old temples intact.

Treasure House of Inscriptions

Tiruvallam temple is a treasure house of sixty one inscriptions. The inscriptions of the Pallavas, the later Cholas, the Pandyas, the rulers and their feudatories the Banas and the Telugu cholas are found in the temple of Tiruvallam.⁴¹ These are the primary sources of information to reconstruct the history of Tiruvallam region and its Bilvanatheswara temple. Most of the epigraphs mention the munificent endowments and lavish gifts made over to the temple in the form of lands,⁴² villages,⁴³ gold,⁴⁴ sheep⁴⁵ jewels,⁴⁶ lams⁴⁷ and various other precious articles⁴⁸ for its upkeep and maintenance. The donors mentioned in the inscriptions are mainly the rulers,⁴⁹ the officials⁵⁰ the merchants and the public.⁵¹

CONCLUSION

The above study makes it clear that Bilvanatheswara temple, Tiruvallam, plays a significant role in the political and cultural life of the Tamils in general and the people of that town in particular. Tiruvallam is one of the prominent town of Vellore District. This town is encircled with a vast stretch of paddy fields and other agricultural lands. This land of religious significance offered settlements to people of diverse communities and religious affiliation. However, this town is mostly free from communal unrest.

Tiruvallam due to its fertility and strategic location, became a vicissitudes of fortune among various dynasties in the end of the medieval period. As such, we come to know from records that this area came under the Pallavas and the Cholas. However, the Banas respective rulers envied one with the other and attempted to introduce various welfare measures including religious patronage. Consequently, all the rulers of different dynasties endowed profusely to maintain the divinity of the Bilvanatheswara temple, which in course left an everlasting legacy in the minds of the Saiva devotees of all ages to come.

END NOTES

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6. *Purananuru, 52.*
7. *Ahananuru, 309: 4-9.*
8. *Purananuru; 198: 9.*
9. *Sirupdnarrupadai, 97.*
10. *Paripadal, 8: 126.*
11. *K.R. Srinivasan, Temples of South India, New Delhi, 1979, p. 8.*
12. *Ahananuru, 287: 7; Paripadal, 4: 67.*
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22. *Purananuru*, 211: 11-13.
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24. *Purananuru*, 232: 3-5; *Ahananuru*, 67; 131.
25. *Purananuru*, 232, 264.
26. *Ahananuru*, 3 p; 4-10.
27. *Ibid.*, 53: 11.
28. *Ibid.*, 131; *Pattinappalai*, 78-80.
29. However, some scholars view that ancestor worship did not develop into a nucleus for the evolution of temples. In support of this, P.K. Acharya states that "the sacrificial altars out of which the temples seem to have grown up were purely a religious structure and had nothing to do with the chaityas or monuments built in memory of the dead..." P.K. Acharya, 'The Origin of Hindu Temple,' *Indian Culture, Vol. I, 1934-35*, p. 89
30. *Kalittogai*, 84: 6-7.
31. *Purananuru*, 299.
32. *Paripadal*, 8: 126.
33. Stella Kramrisch, *The Art of India, London, 1965*, p. 16.
34. *Perumpanatruppadai*, 405.
35. Burton Stein (ed.), *Essays on South India, New Delhi, 1976*, p. 15.
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